

RADNEXT Transnational Access Summary Report

Project title	<i>Reliability of Autonomous Vehicles for Deep Space Exploration</i>
Project TA identifier	<i>TA01-02</i>
General application	<i>Space</i>
Type of test	<i>SEE</i>
Group leader, Institute	<i>Paolo Rech, University of Trento</i>
Date(s) of the experiment	<i>11-13 December 2022</i>
Facility	<i>PARTREC</i>
Amount of access granted (unit of access: 1h)	<i>48</i>

Objectives of the experiments

The goal of this experiment is to evaluate at which level modern GPUs and EdgeAI devices (such as the Google TPU) can be used to accelerate Artificial Intelligence applications for deep space exploration. The idea is to run neural networks in the irradiated devices and understand the error rate and the kind of errors produced by the particles. One of the interesting outcomes of this project is the comparison of the error model (i.e., how the particle impacts the execution of the neural network) induced by neutrons and other kinds of particles.

Experiment test report

We exposed one GPU (NVIDIA Jetson nano) and one EdgeAI device (Google TPU) to heavy ions, mounted as showed in Fig. 1. We executed SSD Mobilenet V2 neural network on the TPU, while the GPU test was not possible for facility problems. Overall, we could perform about 4h of experiments since the beam was fluctuating and not stable.

Fig. 1: beam setup at PARTREC

Despite the low experimental time, we succeed in getting a good statistic on the CNN we tested, the SSD Mobilenet V2. This network was also extensively tested on the TPU with neutrons, which allows us to have an evaluation of the different error rate between the two radiation sources.

Fig 2: weights distribution of the hardened vs baseline DNN

As shown in Fig 2, the cross section for heavy ions is more than 1 order of magnitude higher than the one of neutrons.

Outcome of the experiments

Please indicate what the experiment is likely to lead to by putting an 'X' next to one or more of the possible outcomes below.

Journal publication	X
Data for Thesis	X
Follow-up experiment at same facility	
Follow-up experiment at another facility	X
Other	

As a RADNEXT user, we encourage you to submit the scientific results of your experiments to journals as well as to the NSREC and RADECS data workshops. Please remember to include the RADNEXT acknowledgment into your publications!

RADNEXT acknowledgment:

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